

The Role of Domestic Atmosphere in Shaping Individual Life: A Comparative Study of *Little Women* and *Behind Closed Doors*

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Abstract:

A family is one of the top most secure place for every individual. It is a group of two or more persons related by birth, marriage, adoption who live together. The family is first important social institution in human life. A family with emotions, feelings, psychological and social climate creates domestic atmosphere within home. this domestic atmosphere plays crucial role in shaping the development and wellbeing of every individual. The relationship of every person in family, their communication, parenting practices, atmosphere in family profoundly influence on personality formation, emotional attachment, everything, which individual achieves in his life from early childhood to adulthood. Therefore the aim of this research paper is to explore how supportive and nurturing healthy domestic environment in family fosters appropriate nature, confidence, feelings of love, attachment, satisfaction, respect and healthy interpersonal skills and the other hand how's the negative or non-supportive and conflict ridden domestic atmosphere causes to lack of confidence, anxiety, low self- esteem, aggression, some mental illnesses and chance to be an individual t may transfer into psychopath or antisocial The study examines the influence of positive and negative domestic atmosphere on moral development, cultural transmission, mental health, and long-term life outcomes with the help of two novels first Little Women by Louisa Alcott and second Behind Closed Doors by B. A. Paris. By analyzing both positive and adverse household conditions in a descriptive manner, the paper emphasizes the enduring influence of family environments on individual growth and upbringing. Ultimately, it argues that fostering a harmonious, stable, and communicative domestic atmosphere is essential not only for personal development but also for the creation of positive atmosphere. A person with positive attitude is always fearless, confident, disciplined, moral guide, who can spread positivity and moral values, handle responsibility as well as set himself as a role model.

Keywords: Parenting Practices, Confidence, Anxiety, Mental Illness, Psychopath, Stable, Fearless, Disciplined.

Introduction:

A family is an important social institution. The home is often described as the first school of life, where all family members are role models for every individual in his early childhood. It is a first place which teaches basic values of love, respect, discipline and responsibility. It is a place where every individual first learns, how to communicate, express emotions, resolve conflicts, and understand social norms. The domestic

atmosphere encompasses the tone of interactions, the presence or absence of warmth and support, the management of conflict, and the emotional availability of family members. The domestic atmosphere of family has strong influence on personality and behaviour. Every individual follows his parents in early childhood, therefore all their behavioural manners, their relationship, atmosphere in family, communication, bonding, love, respect to each other matter a lot here. These

all things Unlike temporary social environments, the family setting is continuous and formative, particularly during childhood.

The significance of domestic atmosphere becomes apparent when observing how children from nurturing homes often exhibit confidence and emotional balance, whereas those raised in unstable or hostile environments may struggle with insecurity and behavioural issues. The family environment lays the foundation upon which personality, beliefs, and coping mechanisms are built. Whether consciously or unconsciously, individuals carry patterns learned at home into schools, workplaces, and intimate relationships. This paper descriptively examines various dimensions of domestic atmosphere and its multifaceted impact on individuals by comparing two different novels *Little Women* by Louis Alcott and another *Behind Closed Doors* by B. A. Paris. It discusses theoretical perspectives, emotional and psychological development, behavioural outcomes, academic influence, moral formation, and long-term societal implications.

Little Women is semiautobiographical novel written by Louis Alcott during the time of American civil era. It describes March family, their family bonding, mutual understanding between all family members, support etc. It explains how does March family suffers because of financial hardships, but home remains a site of mutual support, moral teaching, and emotional warmth. In tight and tuff situation every family member remains together with each other and teach values of love, humility, respect, moral introspection, consciousness. Every character in novel, such as Meg, Joe and Beth and Amy leave different traits of their personality shaped by their domestic atmosphere. Many incidents in novel and features of every character such as Joe's independence and ambition encouraged by family that values emotional as well as intellectual support. Meg, his duty explores his sense of understanding others and respect to them. Beth is

also kind and gentle by nature. Beth's nature shows that how is he shaped by empathetic values in her house or domestic atmosphere. Here, March family is an example of best domestic atmosphere where a mother, matriarch lady named Marmee teaches her daughters importance of unity, morality and encourages them to accept challenges. The background and economical status of family is not too strong but we see changes in family members. It clears how good moral, emotional support can change an individual good to the best and cultivate lifelong route for him. If there is appropriate domestic atmosphere with respect and empathy, then any individual can face any situation and can develop creativity, emotional as well as intellectual intelligence.

G. K. Bedi, in his paper 'Impact of Home Environment on Mood Among Young Adults: A Review Study' states that "A supportive home environment improves mood, interpersonal relationships and psychological wellbeing, while negative domestic environments may lead to mental health issues."

Louis Alcott also exposes how any individual can handle any tough situation and also can challenge to social norms if there is a strong family support. Jo, a daughter of Marmee who is tomboyish in nature but literary aspiring woman, who challenges the era's gender expectations. Meg is always busy in her traditional roles but demonstrates that dignity and personal choice can also live within domestic structures. Alcott's novel demonstrates, how freedom and spaces in domestic atmosphere with encouragement and emotional intelligence can support to the creation of multiple womanhood. It has power to develop diverse identities. Further it also explains that how does domestic atmosphere impact on psychological development and mentality of individual. There is an open communication in family members instead of pressure, that promotes family promotes emotional health and

resilience. The open communication allows every family member to discuss fear, disappointments, hopes, problems, each other's capacities, limitations and all things fostering emotional intelligence. There is total cooperation in family members household tasks, which teaches accountability and mutual respect. The total peaceful and healthy domestic atmosphere in home helps to maintain happy, hopeful, respectful, and healthy mentality of an individual, which keeps him away from stress, anxiety, inferiority complex and reduces 80 percent chances of to be a criminal and psychopath person.

Like this, novel of Louis Alcott demonstrates that how does good domestic atmosphere effect in good manner and creates unique personality. It supports to acquire good manners, increases confidence, stability of mind, helps to build belief in others as well as develops inferiority complex of individual. Such individuals make best progress in their career, develop best habits, learn honesty, respect others and learns social norms to be a good civilian. In short good domestic is very important for development of good nature, thinking, education and personality development. There are also other novels which explain On the other hand there are also other novels that explain bad domestic atmosphere can spoil individual's mentality, health and provoke him to be a criminal, psychopath.

Zhou , Y., Zheng , M., He, Y., Zhang J. in his research paper entitled, "Impact of Family Environment on Loneliness, Depression and Education" states that , "Poor family communication and hostile parenting are strongly linked with depression and loneliness in adolescents."

Like this, novel *Behind Closed Doors* written by B. A. Paris is such kind of novel, which lights on how bad domestic atmosphere spoils an individual's life, provokes him to be a

criminal, a psychopath. It is page turning domestic psychological thriller novel. A writer has used different narrative technique that takes reader past and present. It is a story of married couple Jack and Grace. Jack, a husband of Grace is a lawyer but psychopath. He is charming, having captivating personality and tempts to people by his communication. He is psychopath but in society he has achieved good reputation as a lawyer and no one can recognize him as a psychopath, instead of his wife Grace. Jack, protagonist of novel emerges as a criminal, psychopath just because of bad domestic atmosphere and unsupportive parents.

There are number of incidents in novel which reveal how does bad domestic atmosphere in home spoil an individual and how much it can be harmful for anybody. Jack marries Grace, who is also beautiful, loving, careful and responsible wife. She keeps her total faith in Jack but she gets no. of surprises from first night of her marriage. The incidents like Millie's slipping from stairs, Jack's avoidance towards Grace, the location of house far from city and no windows, no mobile to her, for honeymoon when they leave home Jack doesn't care about dog, he doesn't put enough food or water, he doesn't allow to Grace to meet her sister who has down syndrome. He always keeps an eye on his wife, doesn't give enough food to eat, doesn't allow her to go anybody and manipulates Grace, creates confusion in her mind. He also reveals that he murdered his mother in childhood, which further reveals that he all roots of his being a psychopath has been rooted in childhood and bad domestic atmosphere.

The bad and unsupportive domestic atmosphere in his home caused for his such mentality. His father was very rude to his mother, he always used to beat his mother. His mother used to shout, cry but never tried to resist to his father and protected herself. She was total disable woman who just endured whatever her husband done with her. The quarrel between parents

affected on the mental health of Jack. He was getting upset during beginning but later he became lunatic type of person when there was no quarrel between his parents; because her mother's yelling and shouting had become music for him. He was becoming comfortable in it. He was got addicted to quarrel of his parents. Once his mother was trying to elope from home, that time he saw her and resisted from elopement, with the thought that if she eloped, he would not listen music of his mother's crying and shouting.

Like this, B. A. Paris's novel explores that bad domestic atmosphere means constant conflict, lack of love, violence or neglect at home deeply affect individual's personality, emotions and behavior. The home is first place where a person learns values, confidence and emotional stability. If the atmosphere is negative several harmful impact may occur, which we see in *Behind Closed Doors*. Here because of negative atmosphere in home a protagonist becomes psychopath and criminal behind the veil of charming personality and social reputation. Reality is far away from society and he threatens his wife and there we see trauma, fear, depression, low confidence, manipulation and various whimsical traits and sadomasochism kind of personality.

In this way, both novels clearly show how does good as well as bad atmosphere in home affects individual in different ways and transforms individual's personality in both good and bad ways. Both types of atmospheres create such personalities which affect their social, moral, physical and mental conditions and health. Here it clears that domestic environment plays crucial role in the personality development. This comparative study of *Behind Closed Doors* by B. A. Paris and *Little Women* by Louisa May Alcott highlights the profound impact of domestic atmosphere on individual lives.

Conclusion:

As a result, the present research paper by the comparative study of two novels *Little Women* by Louis Alcott and *Behind Closed Doors* by B. A. Paris concludes that the domestic environment plays crucial role shaping an individual's personality. A positive and good domestic atmosphere helps to foster confidence, emotional stability, healthy relationships and personal developments. An individual who grows in such environment becomes best with different social skills, positive skills, handles any tough situation, remains positive and strong. On the other hand, where there is no open communication, unsupportive domestic environment leads to psychological stress, insecurity, behavioural problems and whimsical traits in nature. Therefore, the healthy supportive and peaceful domestic atmosphere is essential for nurturing well balanced individuals to contribute positively in society to be a good civilian to reduce criminal tendency, psychopaths and sadomasochism kind of personalities.

References:

1. Paris, B. A. *Behind closed doors*. St. Martin's Press. 2016
2. Alcott, L. M. *Little women*. Roberts Brothers. 1868
3. Bedi, G. K. & Gupta, A. *Impact of Home Environment on Mood Among Young Adults: A Review Study*. International Journal of Indian Psychology, 12 (3), 678-683. 2024
4. Luo, Z., Qi, F., & Xu, Y. *Family Environment and College Students' and Psychological Health*. Journal of Education, Humanities and Social Sciences. 2023